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Research Paper

Abhadya Churna-A Polyherbal Formulation for Grihadarsi

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ABSTRACT

In modern days due to the change of climate and unhealthy diet, humans are facing lots of diseases. Among them, Grihadarsi, also known as "Sciatic Syndrome," is one of major problems among the 80–90% of the people. In this disease, people feel a pain which is starts from Sphik Pradesh and moves down to foot, and in extreme case, movement of the affected leg has been stopped, and walking pattern also changes like a bird vulture and put the patient in disgraceful condition. It is very challenging to cure this illness in the modern medicine and surgery. Acharya Yogratnakara suggested that *Aabhadi Churna (Abhadya Churna)* is very effective for the Vatavyadhi Chikitsa like Grihadarsi. This churna is also referred in Bhaisjaya Ratnabali, named as 'Abhadya churna', used for the treatment of Asthisandhigata vata, Snayumajjagata Vata, Katigraha, Grudhrasi, Manyastambha, Hanugraha, Kosthagata rogas etc. The present review article gives an overview of this churna including its mode of action, clinical trials and also its individual ingredient's brief overview

INTRODUCTION

The oldest medical system in the world is Ayurveda. In India, more than 5000 years ago, knowledge of Ayurveda is originated and it is often called the "Mother of All Healing".^{1,2} The word "Ayurveda" combines the two Sanskrit words; ayur which is the meaning of life and veda which defines science or knowledge and thus

overall meaning is "The science of life".³ Charak Samhita states that the purpose of Ayurveda is to treat an ill person as well as maintain the health of a healthy person by preventing the coming of diseases.⁴ According to *Bhaishajya Kalpana*, there are different dosage form like of herbal ingredient in Ayurveda life science. Churna is one of the usually used dosage form in ayurveda, also known

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as raj and Kshada. It is a fine powder, formed by mixing certain drugs or combination of drugs. Before mixing, the ingredients are cleaned and dried thoroughly and the pulverized separately. Due to the smaller particle size of churna, it has greater absorption rate hence the greater is bioavailability. In modern times, humans are becoming victims of numerous ailments because of the unhealthy eating habits and diets, change of climate and lifestyles. Gridhrasi is one of the major diseases of the modern era. Gridhrasi was cited by Charakacharya in Vataja, Nanatmaja vyadhi, and also listed under Mahagada, indicating difficulties in curing it.⁵ In this disease, a pain is started from Sphik Pradesh and radiates down to foot. If the patient is not treated properly then in extreme case movement of the affected leg of patient has been stopped, and walking pattern also changes like a bird vulture.⁶ Gridhrasi is similar to "Sciatic Syndrome," a disorder described in modern medicine. Patient with sciatica faces pain from the buttock to the back of the thigh, the calf, and the outside of the foot. In Ayurveda, sciatica is termed as Gridhrasi. More or less 80–90% of the people suffered low back pain in which 5% are victims of sciatica. The treatment of sciatica is a challenge for the modern medicine and surgery. In Ayurveda, it is told that vitiation of Vata which is responsible for the movement and functions of the body is responsible for Gridhrasi. Vitiation of Kapha along with Vata causes Vata-Kaphaja Gridhrasi.⁷ In allopathic medicinal system doctor often prescribed analgesics medicines and physiotherapy treatment which can help the patient to certain extent but these are not the ultimate solution. Sometimes allopathic doctors choose surgery which is expensive, and again there are chances of reappearance of pain as well. In

compare to this, Ayurveda gives better treatment for managing this painful disorder. Acharya Yogratnakara suggested Aabhadi Churna (Abhadya Churna) for the Vatavyadhi Chikitsa, which includes Ajamoda, Sauth, Guduchi, Ashwagandha, and Rasna, among other ingredients. These medications mostly have Ushna Veerya and Vatakapha Shamak properties, which are good for the Vata Dosha and mentioned for sciatica.⁸ This churna is also referred in Bhaisjaya Ratnabali, used for the treatment of Asthisandhigata vata, Snayumajjagata Vata, Katigraha, Grudhrasi, Manyastambha, Hanugraha, Kosthagata rogas etc.^{9,10}

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Authors have searched relevant references with respect to *Abhadya churna* in ancient texts and found it is described various Ayurveda texts such as Yoratnakar, Bhaishajya Ratnavali etc.¹⁰ References related to pre-clinical and clinical studies of *Abhadya churna*, about the individual raw drugs were also reviewed carefully. The author used several online databases like, Google Scholar, Web of Science, Science Direct, PubMed, Scopus, CAS, CABI, HINARI to retrieve valuable publications until now. A number of huge publications related to Grihadarshi and the ingredients of the *Abhadya churna* are carefully read for writing this article.

Ingredients:

Abha, Rasna, Guduchi and Satamuli, Mahausadha, Shatapushpa and Asvagandha, Havusa, Vrdhadaraka, Yamani and Ajmoda, all are mixed in equal quantities and make it fine powder to form *Abhadya Churna*.⁹ The details of the ingredients of this churna is shown in Table 1 and rasa panchaka of the Ingredients are shown in Table 2.

Table 1: List of raw ingredients

Sl. No.	Name of the ingredient(s) in Sanskrit	Common Name of the ingredient(s)	Botanical/ English Name	Part used	Quantity
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01	Abha	Babul	<i>Acacia nilotica</i> (L.) Willd. ex Del. Sp. indica (Benth.)	Steam bark	1 part
02	Rasna	Rasna	<i>Pluchea lanceolata</i> C.B. Clarke	Leaf /root	1 part
03	Guduchi	Guduchi	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Miers ex Hook.f. & Thoms	Stem	1 part
04	Satamuli	Satavari	<i>Asparagus raecemosus</i> Willd.	Tuberous root	1 part
05	Mahausadha	Sunthi	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Rosc.	Rhizome	1 part
06	Satapuspa	Satapuspa	<i>Anethum sowa</i> Kurz	Fruit	1 part
07	Asvagandha	Aswagandha	<i>Withania somnifera</i> Dunal	Root	1 part
08	Havusa	Hapusa	<i>Juniperus communis</i> L.	Fruit	1 part
09	Vrddhadaraka	Vriddhadarak	<i>Argyrea nervosa</i> (Burm.f.) Boj.	Root	1 part
10	Yamani	Yamani	<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i> (L.) Sprague	Fruit	1 part
11	Ajmoda	Ajmoda	<i>Apium leptophyllum</i> (Pers.) F.V.M. ex Benth	Fruit	1 part

Table 2: Rasa panchaka of the Ingredients of *Abhadya Churna*

Name of the ingredient	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka	Karma	Doshagnata	Roghagnata
Babul ^{11,12}	Kashaya	Guru	Shita	Katu	Kaphahara, Pittavahara	Kaphahara	Kasa, Komiroma, Kustha, Atisara
Rasna ^{13,14}	Tikta	Guru	Ushna	Katu	Shotahara, Vatashulahara, Pachaka	Kaphavatahara	Sula, Jvara, Vatavyadhi, Amvata, Agnimandya
Guduchi ¹⁶	Tikta, Kashaya	Guru, Snigdha	Ushna	Madhura	Amahara, Rasayana, Balya	Tridosahara	Jvara, Vatarakta, Agnimandya, Arsa
Satavari ²²	Madhura, Tikta	Guru, Snigdha	Sheeta	Madhura	Balya, Rasayana, Sulahara	Vatapittas hamaka	Doubalya, Vatavikara, Shotha
Sunthi ²³⁻²⁵	Katu	Laghu, Snigdha	Ushna	Madhura	Deepana, Pachana	Vatakaphahara	Amavata, Agnimandya, Aruchi
Satapuspa ²⁸	Katu, Tikta	Laghu, Snigdha	Ushna	Katu	Deepana, Anulomana	Kaphavatahara	Atisara, Adhmana, Sandhivata
Aswagandha ³⁰	Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu, Snigdha	Ushna	Madhura	Sukravardhaka	Kaphavatahara	Kshaya, Vatavyadhi, Shotha, Shopha

Hapusa ³¹⁻³³	Tikta, Kashaya	Guru	Ushna	Katu	Balya	Kaphapittahara	Vataroga, Arsha, Grahani
Vridhdadar ak ^{34,35}	Katu, Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu, Snigdha	Ushna	Katu	Vrushya, Shukra, Ayubalavar dhaka	Vatakaphahara	Shota, Prameha, Vatavyadhi, Mastishkadourb alya
Yamani ^{36, 37}	Katu, Tikta	Laghu, Ruksha, Tikshna	Ushna	Katu	Vatanulom ana, Deepana	Vatakaphahara	Agnmandya, Udarashoola
Ajmoda ^{38, 39}	Katu, Tikta	Laghu, Ruksha, Tikshna	Ushna	Katu	Vatanulom ana, Pachana, Deepana	Kaphavatahara	Shola, Amadoshahara

Important therapeutic uses:

Abhadya churna is used to cure the following all diseases like Asthigatavata (vata confine to bones), Sandhigatavata (osteoarthopathy), Snayugatavata (pain in due to accumulation of vata), Majjagatavata (bone marrow related disorder), Katigraha (Stiffness in lumbo-sacral region), Gridhrasi (Sciatica), Manyastambha (neck rigidity/torticosis), Hanugraha (lockjaw), Kosthagata rogas (All types of disorders of abdomen).⁹

Critical analysis on ingredients of *Abhadya Churna*:

Babul (*Acacia nilotica*):^{11,12}

Acacia nilotica (L.), commonly known as babul is an important herbal plant of tropical and subtropical regions belongs to family Fabaceae of genus Acacia. This plant is enriched with many active secondary metabolites like tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, fatty acids and polysaccharides which enhance its applicability in drug development. The genus of this plant majorly found in Africa, Middle East and Indian subcontinent (Hill, 1940, National Academy of Sciences, 1980, Simmons, 1987). This plant exhibits a number of significant pharmacological activities like antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antihypertensive, antidiarrhoeal and antispasmodic, anthelmintic, antiplatelet aggregatory, anticancer and acetyl cholinesterase (AChE) inhibitory activities.

Rasna (*Pluchea lanceolata*):^{13,14}

Pluchea lanceolata, a small shrub, belongs to the family Asteraceae and genus Pluchea. It grows mainly in sandy and saline soil of hotter parts of India including upper West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Punjab, Rajasthan and Asian countries. Locally it is known as 'Rasna', 'Gandhamula Rasya' and 'Yuktarasa'. This plant is majorly used to for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis allied disorders and neurological disorders. Secondary metabolites like triterpenoids, sterols, flavonoids and lactones are present in this plant. Various pharmacological reports have suggested different biological and pharmacological activities of this plant including antipyretic, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, laxative, nervine tonic, uterine relaxant, anti-implantation and as well as immunosuppressant, contraceptive.

Guduchi (*Tinospora cordifolia*)^{15,16}

Tinospora cordifolia, also referred to as Guduchi, belongs in the Menispermaceae family, is a significant natural herbal shrub in ayurvedic medicine. Guduchi is regarded as a nectar plant and is known by the Sanskrit term amrita for its immune-stimulating, cleansing, and revitalizing qualities.¹⁷ It grows in many tropical and subtropical nations, including Bangladesh, Thailand, Indonesia and Malaysia, as well as the Philippines, Burma, India, Sri Lanka, China, Philippines, and South Africa. Guduchi's roots, stem, bark, and leaves are all edible and medicinally significant portions of the plant. This herb contains a variety of beneficial biomarkers, including tinosporaside, tinosporine, magnosporine, berberine, choline, jatrorrhizine, palmatine, beberine, giloin, giloinsterol, and other phytochemicals classified as alkaloids, glycosides, aliphatic compounds, diterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, phenolic compounds, steroid and polysaccharides, etc. Guduchi is used to treat gout, diabetes, skin conditions, fever, headaches, jaundice, and colds.¹⁸ The herb has been assessed more thoroughly in modern medicine, and most recently, the medication has been used to lessen the side effects of chemotherapy.

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Satavari (*Asparagus racemosus*)^{19,20,21, 22}

Asparagus racemosus, commonly known as shatavari belongs to the family of Liliaceae. This species is widely distributed in subtropical and tropical regions like India, Asia, Australia, and Africa. It goes by the name "herb queen" as well. *A. racemosus* helps to regulate sexual behaviour

and used to treat neurological disorders, hepatopathy, tumors, dyspepsia, and high cholesterol and triglyceride levels. It also helps to increase milk secretion in nursing mothers. It also helps to balance the vata and pitta, improve reproductive and digestive health, help with diabetes mellitus, and lower stress levels. Steroid-derived saponins are its main component. Isoflavones, polysaccharides, asparagine, mucilage, and several forms of vitamins viz. A, E, B1, B2, C, elements like Fe, Ca, Mg and P and folic acid are all found in roots of this plant.

Sunthi (*Zingiber officinale*)²³⁻²⁵

Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe) is an important medicinal plant, widely cultivated in all over the world including South East Asia, India, Mexico, West Indies, China and other countries of the world. In Ayurveda, Sunthi has been defined as Vishvabhesaj, the universal medicine. It is enriched with various phenolic compounds, terpenes, polysaccharides, lipids, organic acids, and raw fibers which make them useful in gastrointestinal, cardiovascular and sexual disorders. Different biomarker compounds like amaldehyde, sogaol, paradol, gingerol etc. are present in Ginger. Sunthi has various biological and pharmacological activities like anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, anticancer properties.

Satapuspa (*Anethum sowa*)^{26, 28}

Anethum sowa Roxb. ex Fleming (Syn. *Peucedanum sowa* Roxb. ex Fleming) belongs to the Family of Apiaceae, is one of the most important aromatic medicinal plant. This plant is widely distributed in subtropical and hot regions of Asia, especially in India, Bangladesh and Pakistan and some European countries. In many Asian and European countries in our India, it is used as a spice for food flavouring. This is also used as medicine in Ayurveda for treatment of stomach-pain, indigestion, hiccups, menstrual disorders, insomnia, flatulence, etc. Essential oils obtained from whole plants and seeds of this plant are used in cosmetics and food preparation industry.²⁷

Aswagandha (*Withania somnifera*)^{29, 30}

One of the most important traditional Rasayana herb is *Withania somnifera* (L.), used from the ancient times. In modern medicinal system this medicinal plant is called as the “Indian ginseng” or “Indian Winter Cherry”. This medicinal plant is mainly used for the treatment of stress, hypertension, asthma, diabetes, cancer etc. This plant also worked against many neurological and psychological disorders like attention deficit

hyperactivity disorder Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, Huntington's disease, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, bipolar disorder, anxiety, schizophrenia etc. It is also used as brain tonic and memory enhancer.

Hapusa (*Juniperus communis*)^{31,32}

Hapusa (*Juniperus communis*) is one of the important herbal medicines, used from ancient time. It belongs to family of Cupressaceae. This plant is majorly obtained in Europe, South Asia, and North America. Various types of biomarker compounds like α -pinene, β -pinene, campesterol, limonene, apigenin, sabinene, β -sitosterol, cupressuflavone, and many others are present as active phytochemical. From pharmacological studies, it is reported that this plant has various biological activities like antidiarrhoeal, anti-inflammatory, astringent, and antiseptic. Traditionally this medicine is used for the treatment of various abdominal disorders.

Vriddhadarak (*Argyrea nervosa*)^{34,35}

One of the important local health folklore and traditional Ayurvedic medicine is *Argyrea speciosa* (Linn.f.) (Family: Convolvulaceae,

Synonyms: *Argyrea nervosa*), also known by the common name Vidhaara. It is the big climber that may be observed up to 500 meters above sea level in India. *A. speciosa* has a wide range of pharmacological activities, including central nervous system depression, nematocides, anticancer, aphrodisiac, antiviral, antidiabetic, analgesic & anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antidiarrheal, and antiulcer properties. The main ingredients in its seeds viz. lysergamides, eragine, and isoeragine—are responsible for its hallucinogenic effects.

Yamani (*Trachyspermum ammi*)^{36,37}

Trachyspermum Ammi, commonly known as Ajacine or Ajwain, is an important traditional medicinal plant with Egyptian origins belongs to the family of Apiaceae. Though this plant mostly grown in Rajasthan and Gujarat, it is found throughout India. Its pharmacological properties have been demonstrated to include antifungal, antihypertensive, antispasmodic, antioxidant, cytotoxic, hypolipidemic, antimicrobial, antinociceptive, bronchodilating, antilithiasis, diuretic, abortifacient, antitussive, nematocidal, anthelmintic, and antifilarial properties. Additional research indicates the existence of a variety of phytochemical components, primarily glucose, glycosides, phenolic compounds, saponins, and volatile oils like thymol, paracymene, α - and β -pinene, γ -terpinene, protein, fat, fiber and mineral matter like Ca, P, Fe etc and nicotinic acid. Due to its stimulant, antispasmodic, and carminative qualities, the fruit has long been used as a major treatment for flatulence, diarrhea,

loss of appetite, abdominal tumors, piles, atonic dyspepsia, abdominal aches, bronchial issues, galactagogue, asthma and amenorrhea.

Ajmoda (*Apium leptophyllum*)^{38,39}

Apium leptophyllum Pers. (family: Umbelliferae) is also referred to as Ajamoda, found in South America, Queensland, India, Sri Lanka, Pakistan, and the tropics. The fruit has long been utilized as a carminative, antinephritic, antirheumatic and preventive measure against tumors, anorexia, vomiting, colic pain, and mitch. Thymol presents half of the essential oils in the seed. Several other phytochemicals like β -sitosterol, stigmasterol,

pentacosanol, 1-nonadecanol, 8-hydroxy cuminic acid, corosolic acid etc are present in the fruit of Ajmoda. Strong antioxidant qualities have been demonstrated by the seeds, in addition to a host of other pharmacological qualities including antimicrobial, antifungal, anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, anti-diarrheal, antiasthmatic, and anti-cancer effects. List of bioactive phytochemicals present in individual plants parts drug and biological activities are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Bioactive compounds in the Ingredients of *Abhadya Churna*

Sl. No.	Name of the ingredient, parts used	Bioactive active phytochemicals	Biological activities
01	<i>Acacia nilotica</i> , Steam bark ⁴⁰	Gallic acid, ellagic acid, kaempferol, umbelliferon etc.	Antioxidant, Antimutagenic and Cytotoxic activities
02	<i>Pluchea lanceolata</i> , Leaf /root ⁴¹	Quercetin, beta-Sitosterol isorhamnetin, pleuchioside, Pleuchiol, pluchea chromenone etc.	Laxative, Anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritis, anti-asthmatic, antimalarial, antioxidant etc activities
03	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> , Stem ⁴²	Berberine, cordifolioside A, cordifolioside B, palmatine D, choline D, isocolumbin, tinosporine, magnoflorine, tetrahydropalmatine etc.	Antipyretic, analgesic, antispasmodic, Antimicrobial, Antidiarrhoeal, anti-inflammatory etc activities
04	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> , Tuberous root ⁴³	Shatavarin IV, asparagine A, racemofuran, racemosol, sarsasapogenin, kaempferol 8-methoxy-5,6,4'-trihydroxyisoflavone-7-O- β -dglucopyranoside etc.	Antioxidant, Antitussive, antibacterial, antioxytocic, antidiarrhoeal,

			antiulcerogenic etc activities
05	<i>Zinziber officinale</i> , Rhizome ⁴⁴	6-Gingerols, zingerone, zingiberene, β -sesquiphellandrene, β -besabolene, β -phelladrene, cineol, and citral etc	Have gastroprotective and hepatoprotective action. Shows antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-cancer and immunomodulatory activities
06	<i>Anethum sowa</i> , Fruit ⁴⁵	Carvone, β -sitosterol, β -sitosterol glucoside, limonene, piperine, furapiole, dillapional, quercetin 3-sulfate, kaempferol-3-glucuronide.	Analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritic, anti-osteoporotic antinociceptive, anti-hyperalgesic, antioxidant, antimicrobial activities.
07	<i>Withania somnifera</i> , Root ⁴⁶	Withanolide A, withasomniferol A, B, and C, β -sitosterol, withanoside I, II, III, IV, V, VI and VII, somnirol, somnitol, withanic acid, phytosterol, ipuranol seudotropine, isopelletierine etc.	Anti-Inflammatory, antioxidant, antibacterial, antitumor, Antihypercholesterole mic activities
08	<i>Juniperus communis</i> , Fruit ⁴⁷	α -Pinene, camphene, quercitrin, pectin, quercetin-3-O-arabinosyl-glucoside, quercetin-3-o-rhamnoside, rutin, luteolin, scutellarein, nepetin etc.	Antiseptic activiy, helpful in rheumatic and painful swellings, piles, and infantile tuberculosis.
09	<i>Argyreia nervosa</i> , Root ⁴⁸	Scopoletin, stigmasteryl phydroxycinnamate, tetradecanyl palminate, 5, 8-oxidotetracosan-10-on, hexadecanyl <i>p</i> -hydroxycinnmate etc.	Anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anti-aging, Gastroprotective, antioxidant, anticancer, antiviral, antidiabetic, antiulcer activities etc.
10	<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i> ,Fruit ⁴⁹	Thymol, carvacrol, <i>p</i> -cymene, α and γ -terpinene, α - and β -Pinene, β -myrcene, o-cymene, α -phellendrene, β -phellendrene, limonene, limonene oxide, γ -terpinolene, 4-terpineol, β -terpineol	Antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anti-filarial, analgesic and anti-nociceptive, hepatoprotective
11	<i>Apium leptophyllum</i> , Fruit ⁵⁰	Thymol, apigenin, quercetin, <i>p</i> -cymene and α and γ -terpinene, cuminaldehyde, β -sitosterol, 1-nonadecanol, 8-hydroxy cuminic acid, α and β -pinene, sabinene, cuminaldehyde, carvacrol methyl ether, stigmasterol, pentacosanol, corosolic acid etc.	Antioxidant, anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal, anti-cancer

Probable Mode of Action of *Abhadya Churna*:

Vata specially Apana and Vyana Vayu Dushti are found in Gridhrasi but most of the time Kapha remains related with Dosha. Since most of the drugs in *Abhadya churna* have Ushna Virya, thus, the present churna have Vatakapha Shamak characteristics. Ushna Veerya drugs can eliminate Vayu's Avarana and also maintaining its natural state. Medicinal plants like Aabha, Rashna, Guduchi, etc. have Katu, Tikta and Kashaya Rasa and thus they have also Vatakapha Shamaka properties. Madhur Vipaka and Guru, Snigdha Guna properties are present in Guduchi, Shatavari, Shunthi, and other herbal medicines which may helpful to eliminate Rukshata from Srotasa. Certain medications, such as Guduchi, Shatavari, Ashwagandha, Yavani and Ajmoda, also possess Vedanasthapana properties. The aforementioned qualities of individual ingredients are all very helpful to balancing the (Vata-Kaphaja) Dosha and normalize Vikrti Dosha and make the formulation *Abhadya churna* analgesic and anti-inflammatory, and help to reduce the pain.

Clinical Evaluation of *Abhadya Churna*:

Abhyadya churna is one of the key traditional formulations that are frequently used for management of painful disorder as it contains Vedana-Sthapana, Sotha-Hara, Deepan, Pachana, Shoolprashaman, Sheetprasamana and Anulomaka Dravyas, which are effective for Vatavyadhis. Guduchi, Vridhadaruka, Shatavari are Rasayan Dravyas and have Balya property that helps in maintaining balance of Doshas and Dhatus.⁵¹ In the year 2017, Renuka et al. carried out a clinical study for the evaluation of efficacy of *Abhadya Churna*, Mulaka Taila in Sandhigata Vata.⁵² Patients were selected randomly from the O.P.D. and I.P.D. of Kayachikitsa from Pt. N. P. A. Govt. Ayurved collage and hospital, Raipur (C.G.) depending upon the clinical features and a detailed research proforma. Patient were divided in to two groups; Group A (30 patients) and Group

B (30 patients). Group A patients were treated with internal use of *Abhadya Churna* and Mulaka Taila and Abhyanga & Swadana with Mulaka Taila for two month and Group B patients were treated with only internal use of *Abhadya Churna* and Abhyanga & Swedana with Mulaka Taila for two months. Though, this medication is highly effective for patients of both groups but Group A patients get better relief from the pain in compare to Group B patient because according to acharya Charak, Taila is best for treatment of vata dosha.

In the year 2021, Bandhe and co-workers carried out a clinical study to evaluate the efficacy of *Abhadya Churna* along with Pathya Aahara and Vihara for the management of Gridhrasi.⁵¹ They have chosen 60 patients randomly from O.P.D. of Shri N.P.A. Govt. Ayurveda College & Hospital, Raipur having symptoms of Gridhrasi and grouped into two groups; Group A & Group B. *Abhadya Churna* (5gm.) with Ushnodaka Anupana was given twice a day to Group A patient and *Abhadya Churna* (5gm.) with Ushnodaka Anupana along with Pathya Aahara and Vihara was given twice a day to Group B Patients for 90 days. Clinical evaluation was done based on the following parameters viz. subjective parameters like Stambha, Ruka, Toda and Spandana objective parameters like standing time and walking time, straight leg raising test. The statistical comparison of before and after treatment efficacy was done by the student "t" test. Experimentally it was obtained that 84% of patients exposed moderate to maximum improvement in Group-B treatment method whereas this percentage was 67% only in Group-A treatment method. Depending upon this assessment, they have concluded that proper Pathya Aahara and Vihara along with medicine is more effective treatment in compared to the treatment with only medicine.

Dosage:

3 to 6 gm twice a day⁹

Anupana:

According to the dosa, the fine powder of Abhadya churna can be taken with madya, mamsarasa (juice of the meat), yusa, buttermilk, warm water, ghrita (Ghee) or mastu.⁹

CONCLUSIONS:

The most prevalent illness in middle-aged and older people worldwide is Vata illnesses gridhrasi. Gridhrasi is characterised by pain or discomfort connected to the sciatic nerve and is quite similar to Sciatica. Sciatica prevalence in the working population is 3.8%, whereas in the nonworking population it is 7.9%.⁵³ Contemporary medicines has limitations giving short-term relief in pain or surgical intervention with side effect. Sciatica is associated with gridhrasi illness. The drug *Abhadya Churna* is a good combination of Vedana-Sthapana, Sotha-Hara, Deepan, Pachana, Shoolprashaman, Sheetprasamana and Anulomaka Dravyas, which is more beneficial for Vatavyadhis. Some of the ingredients of this churna like Sunthi, rasna, shatapuspa, yavani, ajmoda have deepan, amapachan, srotoshodhana and kaphahara properties which help to relieve avarana and proper functioninh of vata. Aswagandha, shatavari, guduchi, vriddhadaru etc have snigdha guna, madhura vipaka, ast as balya, rasayana and asthisandhanakara helps to promote strength. In this review article we have tried to give an overview of this churna and also the individual plant of this churna which may helpful for further exploration of this churna. We believe that this review will help the researcher for further exploration in the field of Ayurveda medical science.

Competing interests:

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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